

European innovation in open and customisable processor architectures

Best practice category

New impetus for chip design. Partner collaboration and open ecosystems. Strengthening manufacturing capacities

Stakeholder group

SMEs and start-ups, Research and Academia

Value chain position

Chip Design, IP, R&D

General Information

Semidynamics is a European company founded in Barcelona in 2016, specialising in the design of **high-performance, wide-bandwidth RISC-V cores**, with vector units optimised for artificial intelligence and machine learning applications. It is currently the only provider of fully customisable **RISC-V IPs**, offering solutions tailored to the specific needs of each customer.

Activities and best practices

- A mainstay of Semidynamics' activity is represented by the development of Cervell™, a fully programmable **Neural Processing Unit (NPU)** based on **RISC-V** architecture, designed to merge **CPU**, vector and tensor computing capabilities into a single platform. The unified architecture of Cervell eliminates traditional bottlenecks between CPUs and dedicated accelerators, ensuring efficient data management. **Cervell™** reflects the philosophy of Semidynamics: fully customisable and open solutions, without proprietary constraints. Customers can configure instructions, memory interfaces and dedicated functionality, including specific instructions at the **RTL** level, ensuring the optimisation of projects in terms of performance, consumption and adaptation to their needs.
- Semidynamics actively contributes to the consolidation of the European semiconductor ecosystem through participation in large research and innovation programmes. In particular, it is a member of the European Processor Initiative (EPI), which aims to develop a new generation of European high-performance processors; also participates in the European PILOT program, aimed at promoting the scale production of **RISC-V** technologies and other open architectures; and collaborates with the European Technology Platform for High Performance Computing (ETP4HPC), strengthening the link between academic research and industry in the field of high-performance computing.
- Semidynamics also contributes to the growth of skills in the RISC-V processor and artificial intelligence sector through an integrated recruitment and training approach.

- The company recruits engineers at different levels, from juniors to seniors, to enhance internal capabilities in strategic areas such as **verification, front end, DfT** and **NoC** design. At the same time, it supports students and recent graduates with **internships** and **master's programs**, offering opportunities for practical work on real projects and mentoring directed by professionals. This combination of targeted hiring and educational programs allows semidynamics to develop highly qualified talent, strengthening the European ecosystem of open-source processors and customised **AI** solutions.

Challenges addressed with this practice

Semidynamics addresses the challenges of increasing AI chip complexity, where traditionally separate CPUs, vector accelerators, and tensors generate latencies and programming difficulties. Its integrated and customisable solutions, such as Cervell™, simplify the development of new AI applications, reducing the risks of project obsolescence. The company also helps to bridge the European gap of open and configurable IPs, strengthening the ecosystem through participation in programs and platforms such as EPI, PILOT and ETP4HPC. Finally, it addresses skills shortages in the RISC-V and AI sector with a targeted recruitment and training model, developing qualified talent and consolidating European competitiveness in next-generation architectures.